

Eurodoc Statement on the Multi Financial Framework

1. Preserve the standalone Framework Programme for R&I

Investments in civil R&I are long term investments. If the FP's budget is absorbed into a future European Competitiveness Fund, the resources allocated to civil R&I will be subject to shifting political priorities, thereby threatening freedom of science. The standalone framework programmes have been highly successful, with the current one extending to and fostering important international partnerships across the globe. Member states, the European Parliament, and stakeholders in the sector have argued with a unified voice for a **standalone framework programme to ensure its continued success** and have emphatically warned against merging it into a Competitiveness Fund as it will erode the stability of R&I funding further and hinder international collaborations.

2. Increase the investments in R&I

Investing in research and higher education is an investment in the future. Eurodoc advocates for an ambitious FP10 of at least **220 billion euros**, with **increased funding to the ERC and the MSCA**. Eurodoc emphasises the importance of national governments meeting the commitments set by both the EHEA and the ERA: **The target of 3% of the GDP for the combined public and private spending on Research and Innovation and the target of 1.25% of GDP for the public sector**. The Commission has invited Member States to activate the national escape clause of the Stability and Growth Pact, which will provide them additional budgetary space to increase their defence spending. A similar measure could be taken to increase the R&I expenditure and to prompt reforms and investments by the Member States.

3. Ensure the responsible use of EU funds and increase the attractiveness of research careers

In order to ensure Europe's competitiveness now and in the future, research careers and careers in higher education must be made more attractive *across* Europe. This means delivering on the promise of EHEA and ERA: **recognizing the professional status of doctoral candidates as researchers by employing them**. As is common in most other sectors, the professional qualifications of researchers should be recognized with respect to their salaries. Most importantly, a mandatory standard needs to be introduced that requires all researchers—including doctoral candidates and postdocs—on research projects financed through EC funds to be employed—the release of any funding should be contingent on employment and access to standard social security. This also calls on the many member states across Europe still lacking legislation for the employment of doctoral candidates to promptly address this.

4. Increase the effects of international research career in Europe

Research has mobility, exchange, and collaboration at its core, which should be facilitated and not hindered by legislation and other frameworks. **Pursuing a research career in Europe can not come at the expense of social security**. The desire for increased international mobility and brain circulation within Europe runs up against systemic barriers such as access to social security, exacerbated by the current nature of the research careers with its short term employment and the hurdles for obtaining (permanent) resident permits. This must be addressed promptly to realise the fifth freedom of the EU and ensure the effectiveness of international research careers in Europe.

5. Automatic recognition of academic degrees

Make automatic recognition of academic degrees a reality. In order to fulfil the vision of brain circulation, of mobility, exchange, and collaboration across Europe, the introduction of automatic recognition of academic degrees—building on the Lisbon convention—is the necessary next step. Similarly important is the work towards the European degree. Both tools—**automatic recognition and the European degree**—are crucial for strengthening **Europe's competitiveness** as well as for strengthening the **shared values and commitments across the EU countries and the EHEA**.

6. Research security and Open Science

Amidst growing concerns about research security, it is important to remember that the result of research is knowledge—and knowledge must be openly shared to hold value for society. Rather than closing off, and in alignment with Europe's values and principles, we should **invest in researchers' and innovators'**

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abilities to uphold democratic values and conduct their research as **openly as possible** while navigating a complex world and changing geopolitical environment. A standalone FP 10, focused on civilian research only, is necessary to ensure that the growing concerns about research security does not erode the open science values and achievements of the last year. Research must remain a public good.

7. Invest in collaborative research and in the humanities and the social sciences

To help overcome the gap of **collaborative basic research** and **complete the research and innovation cycle** in the R&I continuum, a new instrument focussed on collaborative basic and applied research is necessary. Social sciences and humanities expertise must be included to ensure that innovation benefits society rather than disrupts it.

8. Invest in the Widening Countries and peripheral regions

Ensure funding for widening instruments to continue excellence building in the region by preserving and **reinforcing impactful initiatives such as the COST programme**. Enable investment in research infrastructures and in human resources, specifically **promoting the increase of salaries** for researchers to enhance the attractiveness and competitiveness of conducting research in EU-15 countries with respect to the EU-12 countries.

9. Gender equality

Gender equal opportunities must remain a focus of the next MFF. To gain a detailed picture at European and national level, it is necessary to **improve monitoring and evaluation mechanisms** of national dynamics in regard to policies on gender equality, mainstreaming, and intersectionality. Gender Equality Plans should remain mandatory to access EC funds, a policy that has proven itself effective. The eligibility criterion needs to be completed by the introduction of compliance checks to ensure actual implementation of the GEPs.

10. Strengthen the role of science in and through policy making

Consistently promote and **protect scientific freedom**. Scientific freedom needs protection **through EU legislation**. In addition, considering that scientific and academic freedom are values fundamental to democracy, upholding them should be an integral part of soft policy making strategies. In light of the backsliding of democracy experienced also across European countries, strengthening trust in science and in experts is key to ensure a common basis of knowledge and understanding. Particularly with the risks posed by disinformation, a shared knowledge base—including science as providing key reference points—is crucial for democratic cohesion.

About this statement

This statement was signed by the board of Eurodoc 2024/2025 on the xx.xx.2025

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 24 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

